

One Health EJP Annual Scientific Meeting
11-13th APRIL 2022 - ORVIETO, ITALY

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& ABSTRACT BOOK**

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Session Eight: Emerging threats II

O21

ONE HEALTH APPROACH IN TICK BORNE PATHOGEN RESEARCH AND DISEASE XENODIAGNOSTICS – MODEL FROM SERBIA

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Aim: To propose an “One Health” interdisciplinary approach to study the spread of tick borne pathogens (TBPs) between ticks, animals and humans, as well as integration of xenodiagnostic procedures in healthcare management of humans with tick infestation.

Methods: We enrolled 115 patients who presented themselves to the Pasteur Institute Novi Sad with tick infestations. Ticks (n = 124) feeding on human and blood samples from the same individuals were collected. Microfluidic real-time high-throughput PCR system was used to test the DNA of the tick and human blood for the presence of 27 bacterial and eight parasitic tick borne pathogens (TBP). In patients with suspected TBP infection, serological assays were conducted to test for the presence of antibodies against specific TBPs. A field study based on One Health tenets was designed to identify chain of infection components resulting in *Rickettsia felis* infection in one of the patients(1).

Results: Most frequent tick species infesting humans was *Ixodes ricinus*. Different *Rickettsia* species were the most common TBPs identified in the ticks collected from humans. Seven out of 115 enrolled patients developed local skin lesions at the site of the tick bite including erythema migrans, local non-specific reactions, and cutaneous hypersensitivity reaction on multiple sites of the most recent and previous tick infestations (1,2).

Conclusions: One Health approach described in Serbia is first implemented worldwide and will help to characterize the components of the chain of infection leading to human infection by TBPs as well as diagnostics of tick borne diseases caused by emerging pathogens.

1. Banović P, Díaz-Sánchez AA, Simin V, Foucault-Simonin A, Galon C, Wu-Chuang A, et al. Clinical Aspects and Detection of Emerging Rickettsial Pathogens: A “One Health” Approach Study in Serbia, 2020. *Front Microbiol.* 2022;12.

2. Banović P, Díaz-Sánchez AA, Galon C, Simin V, Mijatović D, Obregón D, et al. Humans infested with *Ixodes ricinus* are exposed to a diverse array of tick-borne pathogens in Serbia. *Ticks Tick-Borne Dis.* 2020 Nov 23;101609.